

EXPERIMENT ON USING FLIPPED CLASSROOM APPROACH TO LARGE CLASSROOM.

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Flipping the classroom will lead to increasing student engagement, active participation, and improved academic performance among 3th year Bachelor students when compared to the traditional lecture-based instruction. Despite challenges related to technology and student readiness, the flipping classroom model could offer valuable opportunities for promoting collaborative learning, critical; thinking, and student-centered instruction in large classroom setting. During the class time student tried to participate actively even if they faced some difficulties in completing the out-of-class presentations and e-lectures provided by the instruction of the flipping model could cover their unpreparedness. Different and new lecture format attracted students' interests towards the activities and the course content. Student presentation are most highlighted technique in which student worked well in the course as the main knowledge acquiring and sharing processes were done in this part of the lectures. It worked more immersive by the participants leading the whole group members to cover in the debatable environment. Each presenter was expected to be faced some comments and feedbacks by the members and the instructor as well. Opening up the topic's main content with the help of pre-class materials, in-class clicker questing, and student presentation, the classroom followed the discussion in pair-and-share process. This phase took more challenging part of the lecture as the participants were expected to find some solutions to the critical issues in terms of the topic content. Following these instructions students could master this phase accordingly, despite some misunderstandings in the beginning. These implementations of the lecture experiment contributed to the collaborating learning environment and interactive student engagement.

1. For our research experiment we decided to set several objectives to get expected achievement which can serve as main steps researching our set goal. Objectives of the study as follows:

- 1) To find or create pre-class e-lectures for the lecture topic and implement it to the classroom.
- 2) To find out the level of the students and observe their learning behaviour.
- 3) To divide the lecture groups into treatment and control lecture classroom.
- 4) To improve student engagement, active preparation, and improved academic performance among the students.

- 5) To observe learners' attitude how they going on with new approach with the help of the Likert scale.
- 6) Give them tasks which are more real than fiction in which learners can open themselves freely.

2. *Research question.*

At the beginning of our research, the investigator depicts some predictions and expectations. As it is crucial to make a clear view on what to assume and verify, the researcher highlights several research questions. This paper tries to find answers the following questions:

1. What is the feasibility and adaptability of implementing the flipped classroom approach for larger classroom setting?
2. How does the flipped classroom approach impact student engagement, participation, and academic performance in comparison to traditional lecture-based instruction?
3. What are the main challenges and opportunities encountered when implementing the flipped classroom model in large classroom settings?
4. What are the perceptions and experiences of both students and instructors regarding the effectiveness, benefits, and drawbacks of the flipped classroom approach?
5. How do factors such as technological infrastructure, student readiness, and faculty support influence the successful implementation of the flipped classroom approach?

Methods

Teaching method is a process of interaction between teacher and students, as a result of which the transfer and mastery of knowledge, skills and competencies provided for in the content of training. Acceptance of learning (acceptance of teaching) is a short-term interaction between a teacher and students aimed at the transfer and acquisition of certain knowledge, skills, and abilities¹.

Subjects.

The researcher had to analyze lecture groups to find an appropriate setting for the research experiment. 3rd year Bachelor groups were conducted as a research subject in this research experiment. Lecture group was suitable enough in size to use the flipped classroom model aiming to test its effectiveness and student involvement in larger classroom settings. The group involved 70 students studying in Foreign language and

¹ Consultation for teachers "Methods of teaching preschoolers" // International educational portal MAAM. Ch. ed. Fonov D.V. - URL: <https://www.maam.ru/detskijsad/metodyobuchenija-doshkolnikov.html> Access mode: free. Date of access: 01/10/2020.

literature (English language) faculty so, the researcher decided to conduct the lectures of Lexicography course with the learners mostly English language lexicography, its history, relationship with other languages, and structure . Students asked the researcher to conduct the lessons on using more modern informative tools and interactive collaboration with each other. The researcher created the list of themes and materials for one-month Lexicography course. All the materials and tools of the course were selected depending on the flipped classroom model of teaching. The course lasted a month during the course the researcher tried to implement useful learning strategies and best ways on how to complete an individual practice tests more successfully at home. At the beginning of the lessons, the researcher pointed out the importance of completing prior shared lesson materials and tasks in obtaining target knowledge as needed for each student.

Materials and Equipment

The investigator used the next tools in order to demonstrate the hypotheses:

- a) Questionnaire form – the researcher organized questionnaire form for the students before the opening of the study and after the study in order to know their opinions about lessons’ association, outlook of teacher towards teaching and student and the atmosphere in the lessons before the experiment and after the experiment. This form was actual useful for the researcher as to see how students’ thoughts have been for the research assumed during a months.
- b) Tests (pre and post) – the researcher acquired pre and post check from the students. Pre-test was aimed to clarify how student were worked collaboratively in a classroom and to test their obtained knowledge of language skills and their usage. Therefore, associate the results with post-test. Post-test was aimed to show how learners improved during experimental period over associating the consequences of pre-test one.
- e) Worksheets – these were used during the experiment as the researcher should have conveyed handouts to participators learners for the lessons. Worksheets were taken from different course books and internet websites, and they were purposed to develop observes’ listening, reading and speaking skills.

2. The Equipment

- a) Audio MP3 or computer with speakers – as the researcher is besides aimed to exercise listening skills, this will be used to play the tracks, and speakers make available loud voice for the students;
- b) Highlighter – the investigator teaches strategies while practicing with reading texts, so it might be necessity for the learners to focus on exact or key words and verses from the text;

- c) Audio recorder – while practicing speaking skills, it is given advice to record students' voice themselves in their phones;
- d) Black board with chalks – Indeed, the researcher uses these tools while explaining and clarifying rules and vocabulary for the learners;
- e) Overhead projector – the applicants might show their homework or give information over using this projector. Correspondingly, the researcher might use it for enlightening certain comments or approaches;

Process.

- The research experiment setting is the large classroom and we decided to implement non-equivalent control group design. The non-equivalent groups design is a type of quasi-experimental design used when random assignment of participants to groups isn't possible. It involves comparing two existing groups that are not necessarily equivalent in every way. Despite this lack of equivalence, we can still draw some conclusions about the effects of an intervention by statistically controlling for potential confounding variables. This design is more feasible to implement in large classes where random assignment is difficult. Here's the approach:
- **Groups:** we identified two existing large classes, one that will be designated as the experimental group using the flipped classroom approach and the other as the control group using the traditional lecture method.
- **Pre-test:** created a pre-test to both groups to assess baseline knowledge and engagement.
- **Intervention:** Implemented the flipped classroom approach with the experimental group.

“Watching a video before the lesson and doing exercises and applications in the classroom” is not the only thing flipped classrooms entail. They have also changed how people relate to knowledge and how teachers and students interact with it.

Table.1. flipped classroom intervention.

Post-test: Administered the post-test to both groups after the intervention period.

Step 1

Firstly, all necessary items had been prepared, required information had been gathered in order to be ready for the upcoming experiment and have background knowledge about chosen issue of the dissertation.

Step 2

For our research we chose two groups which were taught in two ways, first one in conventional way and other one experimental group. In our conventional group we taught them in tradition way and the other in flipped way. In experimental group we taught them in inverted way combining the selected out-of-classroom and in-classroom methods in order to comprehend whole class acquiring competence. But before we observed class itself to identify their behavior, level of knowledge, interest. We used classroom observation method. This method helps the instructor to form the classroom for target classroom model. The instructor created an observation table for clear analysis of the lesson.

Flipped Classroom Observation Form

During Observation:

Category	Observation Points	Notes
Student Engagement		
* Pre-Class Preparation	* Do students seem prepared based on their participation? * Do they apply pre-learned concepts?	
* In-Class Participation	* Are students actively involved in discussions and activities? * Is the environment conducive to participation?	
* Application of Knowledge	* Do students use pre-learned concepts to solve problems or complete activities? * Are there opportunities for critical thinking?	
Instructional Strategies		
* Alignment with Learning Objectives	* Do in-class activities align with objectives and pre-class materials? * Do activities promote understanding and application?	
* Variety and Differentiation	* Does the instructor use a variety of teaching methods? * Are there opportunities for all students to participate and learn?	
* Technology Integration	* Are technology tools used effectively? * Does technology support student engagement and the flipped classroom model?	

Tbale.2. flipped classroom observation category.

Step 3

In order to identify pupils' knowledge on the subject acquaintance, we decided to take a test from them structured for lexicography course content. As a result, pre-test was given to the experimental group and conventional group. The task is to put right answers to question about the lexicography. We tried to figure out pupils' problem with understanding of the target classes. Moreover, it would be easy to determine learners' general level, common strengths and weaknesses.

Step 4

The researcher administered content-based pre-test which was completed by the researcher to both the treatment and control groups to assess their baseline knowledge and understanding of the English language concepts targeted in the research. This pre-test included standardized English language lexicography teacher-designed test aligned with the course content. After pre-test the teaching process in the experimental group with the help of interactive methods begins. This stage lasts for 9 lessons.

Step 5

On the 19th of February, after conducting the pre-test on lesson, the teaching process for the experimental group began. To make the lessons more organized and effective the researcher used lessons plans, interactive methods and variety of activities.

Our lesson was begun familiarizing with students and asking the learners about their mood in order to create friendly atmosphere and feel learners free themselves. Then they were asked some questions in order to attract them to the topic “Early history and development of the British Lexicography”. The prepared e-lecture was shared to the whole classroom members by the instructor before the lecture date as they were informed what to do with the shared materials before the course starts. Firstly, the researcher talked with pupils being different personal member of society. The communication had been lasted for 10 minutes. After that, handouts which belong to the topic and exercises were distributed. Students were given quick short questions about the lecture content. They were allowed to use their prior shared material in case of reviewing the meaning of the topic and they have been informed to build a classroom presentation actively. Then the students decided to present their general understanding as a speech about the history and development of the British lexicography. The tasks which were focused on two aspects: clarifying students’ understanding of the lecture content and sharing ideas on topic with each other. It made the students be active during the learning process. The topic was not difficult for the learners as the materials included interesting topic facts with interesting historical steps to development of the British lexicography. As the main reviewing stage was done, the next stage is the analysis of the content related tasks. There students used their critical thinking in solving the problem, did a debate with friends, compared the answer with peers, and produced a summary. Next 8 lessons were conducted in the same way with more practical tasks. The lecture topics were shared with the students and then they prepared either a group presentation or an individual work for the topic understanding and engaging with the subject more interactively. The researcher chose a suitable platform for delivering pre-class materials. This platform was chosen together with the students as they could get pre-class materials without any misconceptions. The course decided to use social network (Telegram messenger), creating TM course-based group. The researcher developed engaging pre-class learning materials aligned with the course content. These materials include:

Video lectures: Concise and informative video lectures or e-lectures delivered by the researcher or sourced from reliable online resources such as YouTube.

Interactive exercises: Short quizzes, clicker questions or think-pair-share activities that encourage students to grapple with the material independently regarding on the students’ preferences.

Readings: Articles, or case studies relevant to the upcoming class topic. Each lesson requires to find well-informed sources from the relevant websites and journals. These

Step 6

The next stage is called post- test. Post-test was the same structure as in the pre-test. Afterwards the teacher gave precise post-test for students. Testing students' gained knowledge throughout the 9 lectures researcher presented both treatment and control lecture groups with the prepared post-test format. Expectation from the participants was at least 50%. After some time, all the handouts had been taken. Then for the next lesson teacher checked the answers. Result was higher than expected with the score of 65%. All the mistakes had been discussed and teacher decided to put the strength to, where the weakness is. Mostly, students' mistakes were in theoretical questions. We put more emphasis on those topics using more practical methods. Student should have detailed information when they want to use them comprehensively whereas teacher goal would not differ with that. After they had been given practices and for confirmation to do some individual works and suggestions to master the theoretical rules, they explained how the format of the lecture did contribute to their learning process.

Step 7

The last step is conducting post-test in *the experimental group* as well as in *the control* one in order to determine how teaching with combining methods and activities in use influences on grammar proficiency of *the experimental group* and compare with *the control* one. The task is to complete multiple choice and filling the open-ended questions.

Data collection. The researcher started studying a lecture group of 3rd year bachelor students in UZSWLU that were conducted lectures from English Lexicography. The research experiment lasted for 4 weeks and during this period the researcher conducted the target course content by using specially designed materials for the flipped classroom approach. As the research aimed to hold and experiment in large classroom, all the materials and data collection sources created to suit the lecture format. Lecture groups were included by 70 students each. As including larger number of participants researcher decided to use online platforms to complete the surveys and questionnaire forms of experimentation process. Collected Data are the followings:

- Observation checklists on student participation levels;
- Pre-test handouts;
- Procedure questionnaires and worksheets that were used throughout the experiment;
- Post-test handouts.

Observation checklist. The researcher decided to form an observation checklist in order to analyze the students' participation and check completeness of their tasks. By completing the checklist for each lesson the teacher analyzed student interaction and their level of obtaining the content of the target course information. Each lesson's aims and objectives were briefly analyzed with the help of forming the checklist of this lesson. The teacher included the steps of how the lesson could be conducted and which stage was the culmination part of the lesson. Doing the checklist form the teacher could sum up on what extent the lesson was organized as expected. The teacher wrote an observation form after conducting the lesson and tried to identify how the lesson was implemented. After working the observation form teacher come up with the new tips to overcome with the problematic points on completing the lesson more successfully.

The observation form was created together with the teachers who helped to conduct the research experiment and conducted the lecture groups before the researcher. Research observation form was highly oriented to check how effectively the lesson was organized and hoe the participants were involved both in-class activities and pre-class materials. Checking and observing student interaction, involvement in each task, and completeness of shared materials were important in reporting the results of the flipped approach.

Pre-test. As have been stated before, the researcher took pre-exam from the learners in order to know their general knowledge levels of English Lexicography and also compare the results after the research. Pre-test examination consisted of asking about the general terms of lexicography. Multiple choice question and open-endedness questions were given as pre-testing examination for the learners. 5 out of 10 questions were multiple choice questions and the rest of the exam questions were in the form of open-endedness where learners were supposed to write their own answers from their own understanding. The researcher calculated each as 0.5 point to have clear calculation. All in all, pre-test checkup delivered easily and results will be discussed far ahead.

Post-test. At the end of the search, the investigator took the last examination from the students according to the course content. It was the same number question techniques with the pre-test, as it was crucial for the researcher to analyze how the students were developed through using methods and strategies during the procedure. Each student actively participated in the post-test experimentation process.

In conclusion, data collection part ended effectively, and all the material collected professionally. The result and analysis of the data will be discussed in the next part of the research paper.

Results and Discussion

In the process of research, we have been collecting the necessary information for establishing whether exploring large classroom through Flipped Classroom Approach can contribute to the effective teaching and more engaging learning process.

In the experiment *the experimental group* and *the control* one was involved. *The experimental group* was taught with the help of flipping strategies including student-centered tasks and activities while *the control* one continued learning in accordance with their syllabus. As a result, they are supposed to be compared with each other.

For determining the both groups general lexicological knowledge, in the beginning of the experiment they were given the pre-test and after 9 lessons of exploring the whole course in flipping format of teaching and implementing them selected lecture format tasks and activities the *experimental* one was conducted the post-test.

Characteristic	Traditional Emphasis (%)	Flipped Emphasis (%)
Lecture-based instruction	80	20
Active Learning	20	80
Pre-class content delivery	20	80
In-class application	80	20
Assessment (factual knowledge)	60	40
Assessment (application)	40	60

Table3. traditional and flipped classroom emphasis.

Table 4. Traditional and flipped classroom emphasis.

This table illustrates the key characteristics of flipping method and traditional lesson conduction. There is a calculated emphasis of traditional and flipped environment

Results from the pre-test and the post-test.

In the checking students’ knowledge in pre- and post-test investigations, I decided to test students’ general knowledge as they had completed 4 lectures before we started the experimenting process using Flipped Classroom approach. For each group was given the same testing papers as there were not any difference while the conducting the lectures, both groups were implemented the content in traditional way of lecturing. I decided to analyze and calculate the pre-test results in Jasp statistical software. This program calculation contributes to the overall conclusions of the students’ competences showing the differentiation of the results. The pre-test process was done anonymously in order not to create any discussions on the results among the participants as the number of participants was larger.

This section presents the results of the pre-test administered to assess students' baseline knowledge of English language proficiency before the flipped classroom intervention.

Participants:

A total of 70 students participated in the research experiment, with 35 students in the treatment group (flipped classroom) and 35 students in the control group (traditional lecture).

Pre-Test results: A teacher-designed test aligned with the course content “Theory and practice of English lexicography” was used as the pre-test instrument. The test assessed the general knowledge of the participants on enrolling course content.

Studebt ID	Pre-Test Score	Student ID	Pre-Test Score
Student ID: TRT- 001	43	Student ID: CON- 01	20
Student ID: TRT- 002	44	Student ID: CON- 02	22
Student ID: TRT- 003	30	Student ID: CON- 03	25
Student ID: TRT- 004	32	Student ID: CON- 04	30
Student ID: TRT- 005	33	Student ID: CON- 05	30
Student ID: TRT- 006	15	Student ID: CON- 06	30

Student ID: TRT- 15 007	Student ID: CON- 31 07
Student ID: TRT- 16 008	Student ID: CON- 15 08
Student ID: TRT- 22 009	Student ID: CON- 16 09
Student ID: TRT- 23 010	Student ID: CON- 17 10
Student ID: TRT- 30 011	Student ID: CON- 18 11
Student ID: TRT- 31 012	Student ID: CON- 19 12
Student ID: TRT- 33 013	Student ID: CON- 22 13
Student ID: TRT- 26 014	Student ID: CON- 21 14
Student ID: TRT- 24 015	Student ID: CON- 20 15
Student ID: TRT- 22 016	Student ID: CON- 22 16
Student ID: TRT- 21 017	Student ID: CON- 18 17
Student ID: TRT- 28 018	Student ID: CON- 20 18
Student ID: TRT- 21 019	Student ID: CON- 21 19
Student ID: TRT- 22 020	Student ID: CON- 18 20

Student ID: TRT- 24 021	Student ID: CON- 30 21
Student ID: TRT- 29 022	Student ID: CON- 32 22
Student ID: TRT- 27 023	Student ID: CON- 23 23
Student ID: TRT- 24 024	Student ID: CON- 21 24
Student ID: TRT- 27 025	Student ID: CON- 21 25
Student ID: TRT- 25 026	Student ID: CON- 23 26
Student ID: TRT- 26 027	Student ID: CON- 42 27
Student ID: TRT- 28 028	Student ID: CON- 28 28
Student ID: TRT- 25 029	Student ID: CON- 31 29
Student ID: TRT- 30 030	Student ID: CON- 23 30
Student ID: TRT- 21 031	Student ID: CON- 24 31
Student ID: TRT- 14 032	Student ID: CON- 25 32
Student ID: TRT- 17 033	Student ID: CON- 22 33
Student ID: TRT- 18 034	Student ID: CON- 33 34

Student ID: TRT- 19	Student ID: CON- 22
35	35
avarage 25.28571429	avarage 23.85714286

Table3.5. pre-test results.

After classifying all the learners’ scores, the mean is calculated according to the statistical formula in Excel sheet program. Pre-test mean score for control group – 23.85714286.

For experimental group the mean score also calculated the same. Overall, experimental group’s acquired knowledge is 25.28571429.

From the table calculations we conclude that there is not much difference between two groups. This test shows the stage

Table.5.

Pre-test result in grasphs.

Post-test results.

trearment group	test scores	control group	test scores
Studebnt TRT:02	44	student CON:1	44
Studebnt TRT:03	43	student CON:2	30
Studebnt TRT:04	35	student CON:3	31
Studebnt TRT:05	30	student CON:4	33

Studebnt TRT:06	34	student CON:5	28
Studebnt TRT:07	35	student CON:6	25
Studebnt TRT:08	33	student CON:7	20
Studebnt TRT:09	44	student CON:8	23
Studebnt TRT:10	42	student CON:9	28
Studebnt TRT:11	42	student CON:10	29
Studebnt TRT:12	43	student CON:11	36
Studebnt TRT:13	44	student CON:12	33
Studebnt TRT:14	34	student CON:13	32
Studebnt TRT:15	49	student CON:14	33
Studebnt TRT:16	46	student CON:15	34
Studebnt TRT:17	36	student CON:16	28
Studebnt TRT:18	44	student CON:17	26
Studebnt TRT:19	38	student CON:18	25
Studebnt TRT:20	48	student CON:19	22
Studebnt TRT:21	33	student CON:20	20
Studebnt TRT:22	38	student CON:21	38
Studebnt TRT:23	37	student CON:22	36
Studebnt TRT:24	32	student CON:23	34
Studebnt TRT:25	30	student CON:24	37
Studebnt TRT:26	38	student CON:25	36
Studebnt TRT:27	44	student CON:26	38
Studebnt TRT:28	41	student CON:27	22
Studebnt TRT:29	40	student CON:28	28

Studebnt TRT:30	33	student CON:29	22
Studebnt TRT:31	44	student CON:30	21
Studebnt TRT:32	35	student CON:31	28
Studebnt TRT:33	38	student CON:32	22
Studebnt TRT:34	46	student CON:33	25
Studebnt TRT:35	48	student CON:34	27
	39.3030303		29.23529412

Table 6. results from the post-test.

As it can be seen from the table 3.9 results there is a significant difference between the post-test results. Treatment group’s average test score is 39.3 while this score is 29.2 in the control group which is lower than the treatment group’s results. This means that well-adapted flipped classroom method can guarantee better results and significant changes in learning and teaching process.

Table 7. results in graphs

Methodological Recommendations for Using the Flipped Classroom Model in Large Classrooms.

From the outcomes of the experiment we can outline recommendations for implementing the flipped classroom model with pre-recorded lectures and video lectures in large classroom settings. In this case, the learning environment can guarantee the following aspects.

Better Knowledge Foundation: Prior to participating in class activities, pre-lectures give students a thorough comprehension of fundamental ideas and important terminology. They are able to concentrate on more in-depth analysis and application during class sessions as a result.

Enhanced Confidence: Students who have familiarized themselves with the content ahead of time feel more comfortable asking questions, participating in class discussions, and taking on difficult issues.

Self-Paced Learning: Students can study at their own speed with the help of pre-lectures. To make sure they comprehend the pre-lecture, they can fast-forward, pause, and go over certain parts again.

Emphasis on Application and Analysis: Higher-order thinking exercises can take advantage of class time when the pre-lectures have laid the necessary underlying knowledge. This could involve group projects, debates, role-playing, and problem-solving activities.

Encourages Active Learning: When students arrive to class equipped with knowledge from prior learning, in-class activities become more dynamic and interesting. As a result, learning becomes more dynamic and students actively apply and analyze concepts.

Personalized Support: Based on students' pre-lecture comprehension, teachers can spend additional time in class answering specific questions or addressing areas in which students may be having difficulty.

Adapts to Diverse Learners: To accommodate a range of learning methods, pre-lectures can be made available in text, video, and audio formats. This gives students the option to select the format that best fits their needs.

Enhanced Time Management: By allocating time outside of class for pre-lecture materials, students develop their time management skills.

Possibility for Deeper Learning: Compared to traditional lecture-based classes, pre-lectures can encourage deeper understanding and knowledge retention by allocating class time for active learning.

In our research experiment we were able to come up with the better results by conducting the class with the clicker questions and warm up activities regarding the prior reviewed lecture content.

Based on the findings and results of the analysis of the data obtained by referring to the research problem, it can be concluded that the description of an increase in student engagement and lecture delivery proficiency through Flipped Classroom courses in larger

setting is the core development of the research. Implementation of improving student integration through flipped learning of lecture format classroom in our experiment was a contribution to the newly set lecture delivery. The results showed that using Flipped model in the expanded classroom can improve students' participation skills which include aspects of self-awareness, trust, adaptability, critical thinking, organizational awareness, attitude, initiative, empathy, integrity, self-control, leadership, problem-solving, risk-taking, and time management, in order to suit the flipped environment. This chapter explained the experimentation principles and the process itself. Chapter covers the results of the experiment with it descriptive. The first part of the chapter devoted to the process and teaching methods of treatment classroom. This part includes the main process of implementing the Flipped Classroom Approach in larger setting. We have added possible consideration during the teaching and learning phase. The second part of the chapter explained the outcomes of the experiment. We explained the outcomes from the pre- and post-tests using JASP statistical software. We uploaded the test scores and attended class hours to measure the difference between the treatment group with the control one. We used Independent Samples t-test measurement and from the results we decided to add tables from group descriptive, independent samples t-test and bar plots to show the differences. This chapter analyzed both pre- and post-tests by calculating the average mean scores and the changes in illustrative bar charts and bar plots. At the ending part of the chapter we tried to include our recommendations and outcome from the experiment.

CONCLUSION

This research investigated the effectiveness of the flipped classroom approach in fostering learning outcomes within large classrooms. The findings suggest that the flipped classroom offers promising results for enhancing student engagement, promoting deeper understanding, and potentially improving academic performance in large class settings. The shift in focus from content delivery to active learning activities in class allowed students to grapple with concepts more deeply and receive personalized support from the instructor. The pre-recorded lectures or online resources provided students with control over their learning pace and the opportunity to revisit challenging material.

To explore the long-term impact of the flipped classroom on student learning and retention in large classrooms the research paper included relevant sources to be implemented to meet the requirement of flipping the classroom environment. . the researcher indicated the shifted changes of the research experiment in terms of student engagement and active learning environment. From the results it can be concluded that the flipping environment can boost the eagerness of the participants towards the inverted classroom environment. The researcher explained every step of the research using statistical data analysis both from the Excel program and JASP statistical software.

Additionally, the investigating the optimal design of flipped classroom activities and the specific needs of diverse learners within large settings would benefit future studies. The used

methods and tasks were more student-centered to involve the classroom in-depth investigation. This work witnessed the experiment on the long-term impact of the flipped classroom on student learning outcomes in large classrooms, effectiveness of the flipped classroom approach in promoting critical thinking and problem-solving skills, and diverse needs of learners within large flipped classroom environments.

Overall, the flipped classroom approach presents a valuable pedagogical tool for educators in large classrooms. By promoting active learning and student engagement, this approach can potentially lead to a more enriching and successful learning experience for all students.

REFERENCES

1. Arwa, Luay, .Asst., Lect. (2022). Syllabus Concepts, Approaches and Types: A Theoretical Account. College Of Basic Education Research Journal
2. Abeysekera, L., & Dawson, P. (2015). Motivation and cognitive load in the flipped classroom: de O'Flaherty, J., & Phillips, C. (2015). The use of flipped classrooms in higher education: A scoping review. The internet and higher education, 25, 85-95.
3. Abeysekera, L., & Dawson, P. (2015). Motivation and cognitive load in the flipped classroom: definition, rationale and a call for research. Higher Education Research and Development, 34, 1–14.
4. Allison, Pham., Patricia, A., Halpin. (2022). The Disconnect in the Use and Purpose of the Syllabus Between Faculty and Students is REAL. The FASEB Journal
5. Aronson, N., & Arfstrom, K. M. (2013). Flipped learning in higher education . Retrieved from
6. Bates, J. E., Almekdash, H., & Gilchrest-Dunnam, M. J. (2017). The flipped classroom: A brief, brief history. The flipped college classroom: Conceptualized and re-conceptualized, 3-10.
7. Berge, Z. (1995, April 1). Computer-mediated communication and the online classroom in distance
8. Bergmann, J., & Sams, A. (2014). Flipped learning: Gateway to student engagement. International Society for Technology in Education.
9. Bergmann, J., Overmyer, J., & Willie, B. (2011). The flipped class: What it is and what it is not.

10. Bishop, J., & Verleger, M. A. (2013, June). The flipped classroom: A survey of the research. In 2013 ASEE Annual Conference & Exposition (pp. 23-1200).
11. Burke, A. S., & Fedorek, B. (2017). Does “flipping” promote engagement?: A comparison of a traditional, online, and flipped class. *Active learning in higher education*, 18(1), 11-24.
12. C., Ben, Farrow., Tom, Leathem. (2021). The Syllabus as a Tool to Enhance Teaching & Learning in Construction Education. *International Journal of Construction Education and Research*
13. Danker, B. (2015). Using flipped classroom approach to explore deep learning
14. Danker, B. (2015). Using flipped classroom approach to explore deep learning in large classrooms. *IAFOR Journal of Education*, 3(1), 171-186.
15. Davies, R. S., Dean, D. L., & Ball, N. (2013). Flipping the classroom and instructional technology integration in a college-level information systems spreadsheet course. *Educational Technology Research and Development*, 61, 563-580.
16. DeLozier, S.J., Rhodes, M.G. Flipped Classrooms: a Review of Key Ideas and Recommendations for Practice. *Educ Psychol Rev* 29, 141–151 (2017). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-015-9356-9>
17. Ebert, E. S., & Culyer, R. C. (2007). *School: An introduction to education*. Belmont, OH: Thomson
18. Ferreri, S. P., & O’Connor, S. K. (2013). Redesign of a large lecture course into a small-group learning course. *American Journal of Pharmaceutical Education*, 77, Article 13.
19. Garrison, D. R., & Kanuka, H. (2004). Blended learning: Uncovering its transformative potential in higher education. *The internet and higher education*, 7(2), 95-105.
20. Goedhart, N. S., Blignaut-van Westrhenen, N., Moser, C., & Zweekhorst, M. B. (2019). The flipped classroom: supporting a diverse group of students in their learning. *Learning Environments Research*, 22, 297-310.
21. Haak, D. C., HilleRisLambers, J., Pitre, E., & Freeman, S. (2011). Increased structure and active learning reduce the achievement gap in introductory biology. *Science*, 332, 1213–1216.

22. Hung, H. (2015). Flipping the classroom for English language learners to foster active learning. *Computer Assisted Language Learning*, 28, 81–96.
23. Hwang, G. J., Lai, C. L., & Wang, S. Y. (2015). Seamless flipped learning: a mobile technology-enhanced flipped classroom with effective learning strategies. *Journal of computers in education*, 2, 449-473.
24. Kumush, Golib, kizi, Jumanova. (2021). A vital impact of syllabus in teaching process. *Science Education*
25. Lasry, N. (2008). Clickers or flashcards: is there really a difference? *The Physics Teacher*, 46, 242–244.
26. Levy, S. (2010). Tabula rasa: Why the new generation of tablet computers
27. Love, B., Hodge, A., Grandgenett, N., & Swift, A. W. (2014). Student learning and perceptions in a flipped linear algebra course. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 45, 317–324.
28. McLaughlin, J. E., Roth, M. T., Glatt, D. M., Gharkholonarehe, N., Davidson, C.
29. McLaughlin, J. E., Roth, M. T., Glatt, D. M., Gharkholonarehe, N., Davidson, C. A., Griffin, L. M., & Mumper, R. J. (2014). The flipped classroom: a course redesign to foster learning and engagement in a health professions school. *Academic Medicine*, 89, 236–243.
30. Nicky, Agate., Rebecca, Kennison., Christoper, P., Long., Jason, Rhody., Simone, Sacchi., Penny, Weber. (2
31. O'Flaherty, J., & Phillips, C. (2015). The use of flipped classrooms in higher education: A scoping review. *The internet and higher education*, 25, 85-95.
32. Ozdamli, F., & Asiksoy, G. (2016). Flipped classroom approach. *World Journal on Educational Technology: Current Issues*, 8(2), 98-105.
33. Pierce, R., & Fox, J. (2012). Vodcasts and active-learning exercises in a “flipped classroom” model of a renal pharmacotherapy module. *American journal of pharmaceutical education*, 76(10), 196.
34. Pink, D. (2010). Think Tank: Flip-thinking - the new buzz word sweeping the US. *The Telegraph*.

35. Stephenson, J. E., Brown, C., & Griffin, D. K. (2008). Electronic delivery of lectures in the university environment: an empirical comparison of three delivery styles. *Computers & Education*, 50, 640–651.
36. Strayer, J. F. (2012). How learning in an inverted classroom influences cooperation, innovation and task orientation. *Learning environments research*, 15, 171-193.
37. Talbert, R. (2014). Inverting the linear algebra classroom. *Primus*, 24(5), 361-374.
38. Tanner, M., & Scott, E. (2015). A flipped classroom approach to teaching systems analysis, design and implementation. *Journal of Information Technology Education: Research*, 14(2015), 219-241.
39. Tucker, B. (2012). The flipped classroom: Online instruction at home frees class time for learning.
40. Wilson, S. G. (2013). The flipped class: a method to address the challenges of an undergraduate statistics course. *Teaching of Psychology*, 30, 193–199.
41. Zainuddin, Z., & Halili, S. H. (2016). Flipped classroom research and trends from different fields of study. *International review of research in open and distributed learning*, 17(3), 313-340.
42. Bliuc, A. M., Goodyear, P., & Ellis, R. A. (2007). Research focus and methodological choices in studies into students' experiences of blended learning in higher education. *The Internet and Higher Education*, 10(4), 231-244.
43. Caldwell, J. E. (2007). Clickers in the large classroom: current research and best-practice tips. *CBE-Life Sciences Education*, 6, 9–20.
44. Eisner, E. W., & Freeman, S. (2013). Notes on composing and composition. *Curriculum &*
45. Fisher, R., Perényi, A., & Birdthistle, N. (2021). The positive relationship between flipped and blended learning and student engagement, performance and satisfaction. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, 22(2), 97-113.
46. Flynn, A. B. (2015). Structure and evaluation of flipped chemistry courses: organic & spectroscopy, large and small, first to third year, English and French. *Chemistry Education Research and Practice*, 16, 198–211.

- 47.Ozdamli, F., & Asiksoy, G. (2016). Flipped classroom approach. World Journal on Educational Technology: Current Issues, 8(2), 98-105.
- 48.Rowland, C. A. (2014). The effect of testing versus restudy on retention: a meta-analytic review of the testing effect. Psychological Bulletin, 140, 1432–1463.
- 49.Ahmed, H. O. K. (2016). Flipped Learning As A New Educational Paradigm: An Analytical Critical Study. European Scientific Journal, ESJ, 12(10), 417. <https://doi.org/10.19044/esj.2016.v12n10p417>
- 50.Bergmann, J.,& Sams, A. (2012a). Flip your classroom: Reach every student
- 51.Brame, C., (2013). Flipping the classroom. Vanderbilt University Center for changes everything. Wired. 18(4), 75-85.
- 52.Education Next, 12 (1), 82–83.Definition, rationale and a call for research. Higher education research & development, 34(1), 1-14.
- 53.Herreid, C. F., & Schiller, N. A. (2013). Case studies and the flipped classroom. Journal of College
- 54.HigherEdWhitePaper%20FINAL.pdf .
- 55.<http://cft.vanderbilt.edu/guides-sub-pages/flipping-the-classroom/>.
- 56.<http://www.flippedlearning.org/cms/lib07/VA01923112/Centricity/Domain/1/>
- 57.In every class every day, International Society for Technology in Education, learning. Computer-Mediated Communication Magazine , 2 (4), 6.
- 58.Network, F. L. (2014). The four pillars of FLIP.